

THE NAVAL COASTAL SYSTEMS CENTER
EFFORT IN OCEAN ENGINEERING

William T. Odum

Naval Coastal Systems Center
Panama City, FL 32407

SUMMARY

A review of selected development projects underway at the Naval Coastal Systems Center in support of Naval missions in the coastal regions is presented. Addressed are research, development, test, and evaluation activities in vehicular hydrodynamics; shallow-water, high-resolution sonar; magnetics; diver life support systems; salvage systems; and underwater nondestructive test equipment and techniques.

INTRODUCTION

The mission of the Naval Coastal Systems Center is to be the principal Navy activity for conducting RDT&E in support of Naval missions and operations that take place primarily in the coastal regions. This includes, in particular, RDT&E for mine, torpedo, and sonar countermeasures, diving and salvage, coastal and inshore defense, swimmer operations, and amphibious operations.

In application of technology to this mission, the Center has made significant contributions to the field of Ocean Engineering, particularly in areas of hydrodynamics, acoustics, magnetics, and diving and salvage.

HYDRODYNAMICS

Over the last 10 years, the Naval Coastal Systems Center has developed techniques to design underwater vehicles to meet specific sensor and system design requirements. These techniques, semi-empirical in nature, predict the stability and response of towed, tethered, and autonomous vehicles as a function of external geometric configuration and mass distribution. By using these methods which have been incorporated into a computer code, different geometric designs can be evaluated to determine which design is optimum for the performance requirements. The method uses available hydrodynamic and aerodynamic data to develop a high speed semi-empirical mathematical model for predicting performance from vehicle geometry data. Detailed design of highly maneuverable vehicles is possible with paneling and vortex tracking techniques.

The process of predicting vehicle stability and performance from geometry depends on the successful prediction of the vehicle hydrodynamic coefficients (HCs). These HCs actually correspond to constants in the equations of motion which relate external hydrodynamic forces and moments acting on the vehicle (e.g., vehicle drag or pitching moment) to the motion variables of the vehicle (e.g., vehicle angle of attack or yaw rate). The techniques for predicting the HCs must be valid for a broad class of vehicle geometries as seen by the two vehicles presented in Figures 1 and 2. This technique consists of: (1) analyzing the contribution of each component (body, fins, etc.) to each HC, (2) computing mutual interference factors that relate how one component may affect another, and (3) summing the contribution of each component with interference effects to determine the total vehicle HCs. The body build-up technique is used to estimate the more than 60 linear hydrodynamic coefficients and 40 nonlinear coefficients.

FIGURE 1. TOWED SENSOR VEHICLE

FIGURE 2. TOWED SONAR VEHICLE

NCSC has an ongoing program to gather systematic data for submersible methods development from wind tunnel tests using the body build-up methods (Figure 3). A series of vehicle nose, centerbody, and afterbody sections and fins have been fabricated to cover a wide range of systematic configurations. Fins are mounted on separate balances to determine their force and moment contributions to that of the entire vehicle.

FIGURE 3. BODY BUILDUP

Several series of tests have been conducted in the NASA Ames 12-foot pressure tunnel. These tests have provided, as a function of bare body coefficients, isolated fin coefficients, total vehicle coefficients, and fin/body interference coefficients for fins in the presence of the body. Both Reynolds Number and angle of attack were varied in these tests.

ACOUSTICS

The Naval Coastal Systems Center has been a leader in the field of shallow-water, high-resolution sonars since its establishment. Shallow-water is a particularly demanding sonar environment with its multipathing and high reverberation, making high-resolution a necessity for any sonar used to detect and classify relatively small targets, like mines and swimmers. In the 1950s NCSC developed the novel array concept used in the C-Mark I Shadowgraph Sonar. This unique array is a segment of an annular array, (Figure 4) and provides a perfectly focused beam at all ranges along the axis of the cone defined by the array. The shadowgraph sonar still provides some of the highest resolution sonar images achievable today (Figure 5).

FIGURE 4. SHADOWGRAPH SONAR

FIGURE 5. C MARK I SHADOWGRAPH DISPLAY OF A SUNKEN BARGE

Most of NCSC's recent activity in high resolution sonar has been in the area of acoustic lens technology and synthetic aperture sonar. Much of the work in high-resolution sonar focused on underwater imaging with thin acoustic lens has been performed at the Naval Coastal Systems Center. A recently developed system which uses this acoustic lens technology is shown in Figure 6. This system consists of a 1-metre diameter, temperature-corrected, six-element acoustic lens on a movable focusing framework. Diffuse insonification is provided by the four projector elements extending out from the lens system frame. The received acoustic signals are scanned by a rotating line array in the focal plane. This system operates at 860 kHz with zoom focusing capability over the range from 10 to 150 metres, and provides 0.12 degree resolution.

FIGURE 6. ACOUSTIC LENS

The application to sonar of the highly successful radar concept, the synthetic aperture, has been researched over the past few years at NCSC. Resolution is limited by the length of the aperture. In this concept, a large aperture is simulated with a small one by moving the small aperture along a straight line, sampling at regular intervals, and storing these samples in a computer. Later, by recalling a large number of these samples simultaneously, a large aperture can be synthesized. NCSC has successfully demonstrated the feasibility of the synthetic aperture sonar concept for producing high resolution images in a series of tests using sonars mounted on conventional towed bodies, as well as tests conducted on the NCSC Rail Facility. This work has demonstrated the remarkable potential of this sonar, and has defined its motion compensation requirements; in other words, how far can it deviate from a straight-line course before having to correct the signals?

MAGNETICS

Since the early 1970s, the Naval Coastal Systems Center has pioneered efforts to develop state-of-the-art superconducting magnetic sensors and associated signal processing algorithms directed at providing the Navy with improved detection, localization, and classification capability against magnetic targets.

Superconducting magnetic sensors, which are based on application of Josephson's junction SQUID technology, have several unique desirable features. Superconducting magnetic sensors can be configured as compact single or multiple element magnetometers or gradiometers with unprecedented high sensitivity

(100 or more times greater sensitivity than equivalent size conventional magnetic sensors). They are broadband sensors which, in particular, respond linearly to magnetic signals well below 1 Hz. Configured as a gradiometer, superconducting magnetic sensors reject ambient noise due to temporal geomagnetic fluctuations which often limit the usable sensitivity of conventional sensors operating in the earth's magnetic field. A superconducting magnetic sensor can be designed as a multi-element gradiometer providing multiple independent gradient measurement information or a magnetic target on an environmental magnetic source such as ocean waves or a geologic anomaly.

NCSC has developed and field tested several superconducting magnetic sensors for both stationary and towed operations. Early version sensors, such as the five gradient sensor shown in Figure 7, were developed for stationary operations with the superconducting elements immersed directly in liquid helium. The dewar for this sensor included a large 100-litre reservoir which provided 30-day operation time. Key issues which were successfully addressed during development of this sensor included development of sensor RF immunity techniques, and gradiometer balancing (loop area and orientation matching) techniques.

FIGURE 7. STATIONARY SUPERCONDUCTING MAGNETIC SENSOR

More recently a new five-gradient superconducting sensor has been developed which is configured for towed operation. The sensor probe is shown in Figure 8. This sensor operates in a horizontal dewar and includes an improved DC SQUID which has increased the sensitivity by a factor of five or more over previous SQUIDS. The sensor includes superior gradiometer balance techniques and eddy current compensation techniques to reduce sensor noise due to motion.

Recently, preliminary flight tests were performed with the sensor towed behind a P-3C aircraft (Figure 9). Full five-gradient operation was demonstrated in flight at noise levels comparable to simulated flight motion on the ground. Improvements in gradiometer balance are being made prior to full sensitivity flight tests. Underwater tow tests with a similar sensor are planned in the future.

FIGURE 8. TOWED HORIZONTAL SENSOR

FIGURE 9. TOWED SENSOR VEHICLE

In addition to Navy applications, the new towed five-gradient sensor will serve as a valuable measurement tool for studying magnetic signals and models of ocean waves, and provide superior measurements to aid in magnetic geologic surveying and modeling.

LIFE SUPPORT

The MK 14 Mod 0 Closed Circuit Saturation Diving System (CCSDS) is a recent development for the life support of saturation divers to perform deep water salvage and rescue missions. This system is intended for supplemental use with the Navy's MK 2 Mod 0 and Mod 1 Deep Dive System (DDS). It is designed to provide a safe reliable saturation diving system for use by excursion divers from a Personnel Transfer Capsule (PTC) to depths of 1000 feet. The MK 14 is designed to use many of the assets of the host DDS to which it interfaces. The normal operation of the system is entirely closed circuit. Diver's breathing gas is taken from the controlled PTC atmosphere, pumped to the diver for respiration via an umbilical, then the exhaust (exhaled) gases are returned to the PTC atmosphere for CO₂ removal and controlled O₂ replenishment. The more conventional mixed-gas systems for deep dive applications use and waste large quantities of helium.

The MK 14 system uses a unique push/pull pump to conserve helium and enable reuse of the precious gas. The MK 14 Mod 0 CCSDS program is sponsored by the Naval Sea Systems Command (SEA 05R4) (Figure 10).

FIGURE 10. MK 14 SYSTEM

Because of the very critical life-support aspects of a new saturation diving system, many hours of unmanned tests of components and of the integrated system were undertaken to demonstrate reliability. A controlled series of manned tests of the system were conducted during 1977 in the Ocean Simulation Facility by the Navy Experimental Diving Unit and medical personnel to depths of 1100 feet. These tests were successful and validated system performance for the procurement of an advanced development model (ADM) for TECHEVAL and OPEVAL. The ADM has been procured, tested, and interfaced with the MK 2 Mod 0 DDS PTC aboard the DTV ELK RIVER (IX-501).

The MK 14 Mod 0 CCSDS system is composed of four major subsystems: (1) the diver-worn equipment, (2) the umbilical, (3) the pump package, and (4) the PTC interface and control equipment (Figure 10). This system is designed to allow diver depth excursions of 100 feet below and 33 feet above the PTC between operating depths of 200 to 1000 feet. The CCSDS extends the diver's capability for doing work at greater depths and for longer periods of time.

The diver-worn equipment includes the MK 14 helmet with neck ring, neck dam and attachment fittings, a commercially available standard hot water suit modified to interface with MK 14 gear; i.e., the helmet, umbilical, and breathing gas heater, all of which attach to the suit.

The helmet assembly is uniquely MK 14 and differs from other saturation dive helmets in its push/pull gas supply-return functions. Gas and electrical connections are external and located at the rear of the helmet's metal base. Breathing gas mixtures pass through a check (non-return) valve, a supply valve, and into the helmet interior through a muffler. Exhaust gas exits the helmet through the safety exhaust valve and a back-pressure regulator. In the event of regulator or pump package malfunction, emergency breathing gas from PTC emergency stores are supplied to the diver and is vented from the helmet to the sea through a helmet manual exhaust valve to prevent helmet over-pressure. Normally, the regulator controls the flow of breathing gas out of the helmet and into the return hose of the umbilical. The regulator is a back-pressure sensitive device that maintains a small positive pressure in the helmet relative to ambient seawater pressure and over a wide range of flow rates. The regulator permits gas flow within the approximate range of ± 4.0 inches of water over/under-pressure in order to prevent a CO_2 buildup in the helmet for a wide range of diver work rates. The MK 14 system provides a flow rate of breathing gas through the helmet of 6 actual cubic feet per minute.

The umbilical is composed of a bundle of married hoses for gas supply, gas return, hot water, pneumofathometer (to monitor diver excursions in depth), and a communications cable plus appropriate connectors and fittings for attachments at the diver and at the PTC. Umbilical lengths to 250 feet were successfully tested at NCSC.

The push/pull pump is the unique heart of the MK 14 CCSDS. The pump packages, one for each of two divers, mount as separate assemblies in locations provided on an external rack on the PTC. Connections between the pump packages and PTC provide electrical power, control, monitoring of functions, alarm systems, and flow of gas. The umbilical, connecting the diver to the PTC, provides a flow path for breathing gas. The push/pull pump motor frame assembly is housed in an internally finned, sealed pressure vessel and consists of an electric motor with double-ended shaft to drive a supply pump assembly; a return pump assembly; and various components for control, distribution, and monitoring of unit functions. The pump package operates in a push/pull mode. That is, the supply pump pushes the breathing gas mixture to the diver and the return pump pulls the exhaled gas from the diver back to the pump and PTC. Each pump has eight cylinders operating in a paired sequence to minimize pressure pulsations.

SALVAGE

The large object salvage system (LOSS) was designed to lift heavy objects up to 3000 tons from depths to 850 feet. The system consists of two major components: the salvage pontoon and the pontoon emplacement vehicle (PIV). The pontoon provides a self contained lift capability of 100 tons with de-watering being accomplished with compressed air or liquid nitrogen (LN_2). Compressed air is supplied by a hose from the surface in shallow water and LN_2 is carried in 1800 gal dewars on board the pontoon for de-watering in deeper depths.

The pontoon is a thin walled cylinder 13 feet in diameter by 50 feet long and must be pressure compensated at all depths. Pressure compensation is accomplished by precise control of the de-watering medium. The cylinder is compartmented into a large floodable center compartment providing the 100-ton variable

lift capability, and two end compartments that provide neutral buoyancy to the total pontoon and also house the LN₂ dewars and the control electronics. Four articulated arms are used to attach the pontoon to the object to be recovered. Each arm is fitted with a pad containing explosive activated studs capable of penetrating 2 inches of HY 80 steel to nail the pad to the object. Each arm also contains a half shot of 4-inch anchor chain that is dropped to the bottom to control excess buoyancy required to overcome break out loads when starting the initial lift.

The PIV is designed to mate with a pontoon near the surface and fly the pontoon to a precise position on the object to be recovered. It maintains that position until the arms are lowered and the explosives are fired to nail the arm to the object to be recovered. Propulsion is provided by five 30 horsepower electric motors driving 48 inch four bladed propellers. It is equipped with a bottom referenced acoustic navigation system, two low light level TV systems, two buoyancy tanks providing 2000 pounds of variable buoyancy and a power/control umbilical.

A demonstration system consisting of a PIV and two 100-ton pontoons along with control, handling, and power systems was fabricated by NCSC to provide feasibility of the technique and to demonstrate the capability of operating from a craft of opportunity (Figure 11). A 180-ton test object was placed in the Gulf of Mexico in 130 feet of water. The pontoons were successfully placed on the test object and the total assembly lifted to the surface. Sea conditions during the operations consisted of state 4 seas and currents of 2 knots (Figure 12).

FIGURE 11. LOSS PONTOON PIV

FIGURE 12. LOSS DEMONSTRATION SYSTEM

SHIP HUSBANDRY

NCSC has performed development work in underwater nondestructive testing (NDT) which provides Navy divers and NDT personnel with tools that allow accurate inspection of waterborne ships. This provides the Navy with the capability of making important maintenance or repair decisions in advance of scheduled dry dockings. In general, when inspections are performed by Navy divers using NCSC equipment, the results are in a tangible form, rather than verbal, and are nearly devoid of the divers' subjective impressions; this lends credibility to the results and fosters their use by engineering personnel. Three complementary techniques have been addressed to date: stereophotography, ultrasonic inspection, and magnetic particle inspection.

Stereophotography is particularly well suited to documenting the condition of ship's hulls. The camera apparatus developed for this task takes pictures of an area about 3 in. x 5 in., with stereo coverage of an area about 3 in. x 3 in. This close-up documentation is appropriate for gathering engineering quality visual data on corrosion pitting, paint blistering, marine fouling, and visible cracks. The apparatus used by the diver incorporates a fixed camera-to-hull distance so that all camera and strobe settings can be set before the dive, and one is assured that focus and lighting will be correct for nearly every exposure. Additionally, the apparatus allows sequential exposures to be made from a right and a left position, giving a stereo pair of photographs, from which elevations can be measured with

an accuracy better than ± 0.05 in. The diver is, of course, responsible for taking pictures of representative conditions on the hull, but he needs virtually no skill in photography to produce consistently excellent results.

Ultrasonic inspection has been applied to hull plate thickness gauging. Plate thickness is an important consideration when evaluating a ship's structural integrity or when specifying future work in dry-dock. The NCSC-developed system uses a team comprising a diver, a certified ultrasonic inspector, and a desktop computer. The diver carries the transducer to various locations on the hull, and is responsible for accurately locating himself and reporting his position, but he is not responsible for adjusting the ultrasonic instrument or interpreting its display. The ultrasonic inspector stays topside, directing the diver to particular hull locations, adjusting the instrument, and controlling the computer. The computer takes bursts of ultrasonic thickness readings and processes them to extract relevant structural information. It also stores all readings, the location at which they were taken, the diver's visual observations, and calibration information. Later, the computer is used to produce reports formulated to engineering requirements. Again, in this system, NCSC-developed hardware relieves the diver of acting as an uncertified inspector, and it produces hard-copy records which may be analyzed in detail at any later date.

Magnetic particle inspection is a fairly straightforward means of enhancing the visibility of surface-opening cracks in steel. NCSC has provided magnetic particle inspection kits to Fleet diving activities so that the divers can accurately document cracks. Their work can be viewed on TV by certified magnetic particle inspectors, and the close-up stereophotographic apparatus can be used to make permanent and objective records of the results. This technique is also used in conjunction with underwater weld repairs to ensure the quality of the weld.

NCSC continues development work in underwater NDT applied to non-metallic sonar domes, non-ferrous hull appurtenances and advanced signal processing techniques. In all these endeavors the hardware and techniques are intended to limit the subjectivity of the results and enhance the engineering value of the information brought topside.